

BIOMASS – A SUSTAINABLE SOURCE OF ENERGY IN MOUNTAIN AREAS

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Abstract

The context created by the energy crisis and the climate crisis calls for renewable, ecological, environmentally-friendly energy solutions that support sustainable development. Alternatives to fossil fuels include biomass (either forestry and/or agricultural) as a renewable energy source. It is estimated that both forests and agricultural activities generate a significant amount of biomass that could be used for energy production.

The aim of the analysis is to identify the potential and possibilities of using biomass as an energy source in mountain areas.

The study shows that mountain areas have sufficient forest and agricultural biomass, so that it can be considered an important pillar in a future energy strategy for mountain areas. Among the main sources of biomass specific to mountain areas include residues from forestry, residues resulting from wood processing, crop residues, biomass resulting from cutting orchards or vineyards (where this is an activity specific to the area). Also, animal husbandry is another branch that generates biomass that can be used as a heating agent for mountainous areas. An important source of biomass can also be unproductive marginal lands, on which energy crops can be created.

The possibilities of using biomass as an energy source can be realized through family biogas installations, improved stoves distributed at the household level, or even biomass power plants serving a network of villages or a city located in mountainous areas.

The results obtained will be able, through the information provided, to help decision-makers to view biomass as a sustainable energy source that can be used on a large scale.

Keywords: *biomass, renewable energy, forest biomass, agricultural biomass, sustainable development, energy politics.*

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring energy needs has become a global challenge. The growing demand for energy, driven by industrialization and population growth, has led to the overexploitation of conventional sources (coal, oil, natural gas), which will lead to both their depletion and environmental degradation. Research estimates that oil reserves, for example, will be depleted by 2060, and even if new sources of oil are discovered, the threat remains (Saleem 2022).

Another challenge associated with conventional energy sources is their environmental impact. Their combustion is estimated to release significant amounts of CO₂ (about 21.3 billion tons) and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere (Saleem 2022).

The context created by these crises requires the identification of alternative energy sources that can make a significant contribution to the energy supply, and which at the same time, are in accordance with ecological principles.

Alternative solutions to conventional energy sources, widely accepted, are those related to hydropower, solar energy, wind energy, energy generated by the use of biomass, geothermal energy and ocean energy.

The transition to sustainable energy, using renewable sources, is a topic on the political agenda of many countries. At the European level, for example, concerns about renewable energy sources start with the 1997 *Kyoto multilateral protocol*, which, includes the use of renewable sources for energy among other development objectives. Today, renewable energy sources are supported, among other policies, by Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of renewable sources of energy, which has been amended several times so far.

It is therefore accepted that a shift towards a sustainable energy supply is a matter of urgency (Steubing et al. 2010). Efficient and sustainable solutions to develop a clean energy system therefore seem to come from the use of renewable energy sources (Zhang and Long 2010).

Among these energy sources, biomass has good future potential given its global distribution, diversity and environmental benefits (Zhang and Long 2010). It is estimated that biomass could be among the main energy sources globally in the coming years, contributing significantly to the development of sustainable energy systems and sustainable development in both industrialized and developing countries (Hall 1997; Bernades et al. 2003). By 2050, it is reported that 50% of the energy needs in developed countries will be covered by biomass as a feedstock (Saleem 2022). Moreover, it could be a significant pillar in ensuring energy security, due to its widespread use in most countries of the world (Saleem 2022).

Mountain areas, due to the rich biodiversity (hosting 23% of the world's forests), agricultural activities, but also the availability of unproductive marginal lands, although considered disadvantaged, have significant biomass resources. Starting from this state of affairs and correlating it to the provisioning provided by the energy crisis, we can ask ourselves to what extent biomass can support a sustainable energy system in the above-mentioned areas.

This paper aims to identify and analyze the potential and possibilities of using biomass as an energy source in mountain areas.

In order to achieve this goal, the study will first approach a descriptive method (description, synthesis) which will allow us to define biomass and identify its sources in mountain areas. A second stage will require an analysis of the opportunities for using biomass as a renewable energy source in mountain areas.

For data collection we used databases such as *Google Academic*, *Google scholar*, *Scopus*, *Science open*, *Science Direct*, *Wiley Online Library*, using keywords such as: *biomass*, *renewable energy sources*, *waste*, *mountain biomass*, *biomass sources in mountain areas*.

The conclusions reached highlight the fact that biomass used as a renewable energy source can develop a sustainable energy system for mountain areas, with the prospect of economic development and energy independence, but under the conditions of regulation, which does not allow the destruction of other balances (such as environmental degradation or the impact of agricultural activities specific to mountain areas).

METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach is specific to a review study. It involved the use of significant databases (Google Academic, Google scholar, Scopus, Science open, Science Direct, Wiley Online Library) in order to identify the specialized literature covering the topic.

Keywords used to obtain publications appropriate to the topic: biomass, renewable energy sources, waste, mountain biomass, biomass sources in mountain areas.

The data search stage gave us an initial base consisting of a number of 193 articles. For these articles, the title, summary, and conclusions were analyzed to identify whether the research is necessary for our analysis. Following this examination, 38 articles were selected, which were reviewed in their entirety, and which formed the basis of this study. The relatively small number of articles remaining for this analysis can be argued by the fact that studies on the potential and availability of biomass as a renewable energy source in mountain areas are limited. Most studies conducted on this topic are available at the global, continental, and country levels.

Only English-language and Romanian-language publications were analyzed for the time span 1990-2023.

RESULTS

a. Biomass (terminology) and biomass sources

The most abundant renewable resource on the planet is considered to be biomass (Câmpeanu 2014), with the potential to become one of the main sources of energy in the coming years (Berndes et al. 2003).

This, is broadly defined "as organic matter derived from living or recently living organisms (Lewandowski et al. 2018), or anything that can be represented by biologically produced matter (Demirbas 2004). Another definition, which can be found in European legislation and reports, appreciates biomass "as a biodegradable part of products, wastes and residues of biological origin resulting from agricultural, forestry, industrial activities, including municipal waste" (Directive 2009/28/EC), but also as "a renewable biological resource that can be converted into value-added products such as food, feed and energy" (European Commission 2012).

Biomass was first defined in the 1927s by zoologist Reinhard Demoll, who understood biomass to be "an amount of substance from living organisms per unit surface area or volume" (Zörb and Lewandowski, 2018).

Although biomass is an increasingly used concept, especially in the context of sustainable energy strategies, specialized literature does not give a standard definition (Zörb and Lewandowski 2018), but rather it is shaped by uses and sector of use.

The multitude of definitions attributed to biomass reveals the diversity of sources from which it comes.

Biomass can therefore be classified according to several criteria: **its origin** (*plant, animal and micro-organism*), the **sector from which it comes** (*agricultural, forestry biomass or various industrial wastes*), respectively **its main component** (*starch, lignocellulose, oil or protein*).

The use of biomass began in prehistoric times with the discovery of fire, and today it is considered one of the most important energy alternatives that could make a significant contribution to sustainable development. Its importance lies in the fact that it can be used to produce electricity and thermal energy, but also, to the same extent, for the production of biofuels.

The context created by the current energy crisis draws biomass as a "green" energy source into the discussion on sustainable energy strategies.

Among the myriad sources of biomass used for energy production that do not compete with food needs and land availability are: animal residues, forestry

residues/waste, industrial residues, energy crops (grown on marginal lands), surplus cereals, municipal waste, wastewater, agricultural residues and waste.

Therefore, biomass is regarded as a complex renewable matter of biological origin characterized by significant chemical variability (Adeleke et al. 2023).

b. The potential of biomass as a renewable energy source for mountain areas

The current energy crisis calls for sustainable strategies to achieve energy security. Among the areas that could develop energy systems to ensure their energy needs are mountain areas, thanks to their biomass sources they have.

The specific characteristics of mountain regions are considered to be important sources of biomass. The most common are agricultural and forestry nature, as well as biomass from marginal non-productive land. Studies such as those developed by Katsoulakos and Kaliampakos (2018), on the use of biomass as an energy source in a mountainous region in Greece, state that the mountain town of Metsovo has 15,800 tons of forest biomass per year, of which less than half is sufficient to provide caloric energy for 70% of the local population. For the mountainous area of Greece, the energy potential of forest biomass represents an important resource for local populations, while the recovery of agricultural residues and those resulting from farmers' activity is quite low (Katsoulakos and Kaliampakos 2018). The potential and availability of biomass as an energy source for mountain areas have also been studied in Northern Italy. Fiorese and his collaborators analyzed, from both an energy and economic perspective, biomass-based energy supply systems in three districts in the aforementioned area, namely Como - a predominantly mountainous region, Piacenza - with mountainous and plain areas, and Cremona - a predominantly plain area. The study showed that there are available biomass sources (forest residues, residues from the wood industry, biomass from agricultural crops or from short rotation forestry plantations) for their use for energy purposes, and that the use of biomass generates energy benefits (2.5%-6% of total energy consumption), environmental benefits through reduced carbon emissions (1.1%-8.4% compared to 2001), and economic benefits (Fiorese et al. 2006). The assessment of the energy potential of mountain areas has also been analyzed in countries such as India. In this sense, a study carried out in the 2010s by Kanase-Patil, together with his collaborators, highlights that biomass (agricultural and forest) is the second most important source of energy (equivalent to 198556 kWh/year) for the inhabitants of the mountain village of Almora district, India. It is well known that mountain forests cover 9 million km² which represents a significant proportion (23%) of the total forests on the Earth's surface (Price et al. 2011). These can be an important source of biomass for a possible energy strategy. Today, forest biomass seems to be most often used to generate thermal energy. For mountainous areas, studies (Freppaz et al. 2004) show that forest biomass production mainly satisfies local thermal energy needs. The results of a study (Valente et al. 2011) on bioenergy from mountain forests in Norway conclude that woody biomass would be an important raw material for energy production, noting that there is an untapped potential of wood and residues from logging activities. Also, studies such as Kanzian from 2006 or Spinelli and Magahotti from 2009, assess that, technically, the use of forestry residues from mountain forests presents high potential for the energy industry. Also, an analysis of the potential of biomass (forest and agricultural residues) as an energy source was carried out in the area of the Italian Cinque Terre National Park. The mentioned park includes coastal, mountainous and agricultural landscapes. The authors of the study (Garcia et al. 2015) state that protected areas can provide different types of biomass, starting with residues resulting from silvicultural cuttings, agricultural residues, respectively residues from farms. The studied area (Italian Cinque Terre National Park) has a multitude of

biomass sources, but the most common is biomass resulting from the cutting of vines (Garcia et al. 2015). The studied area (Italian Cinque Terre National Park) has a multitude of biomass sources, but the most common is biomass resulting from the cutting of vines (Garcia et al. 2015). From the forest sector, biomass, which could be available for energy use, results both from logging activities, forest management, wood processing and in the form of old furniture. Mountain regions are home to 10% of the global population, where woody biomass provides 90% of total energy consumption (Price and Butt 2000).

In addition, agricultural/zootechnical activities specific to mountain areas can also provide a significant biomass input in the form of residues from agricultural crops or orchards, manure, and residues from agroforestry systems. For sustainable energy production, agricultural biomass, is a possible precursor material (Saleem 2022).

It is estimated that one of the potential sources of energy generation in the highlands is represented by forestry and agricultural residues (Saleem 2022). In Basilicata, a predominantly mountainous region in southern Italy, the regional administration initiated a study on the production of energy from renewable sources, in particular from the use of biomass (Romano and Cozzi 2005). The results of the study reveal that the potential availability of agricultural biomass is approximately 50,000,000 kg/year, mainly from the felling of olive plantations, of forest biomass of 1,660,000 kg/year, respectively of biomass represented by residues from wood processing industries of 325,000 kg/year (Romano and Cozzi 2005). The development of an energy industry based on biomass presents considerable economic, ecological and social advantages (Romano and Cozzi 2005).

Biomass sources in mountain areas can be supplemented, in addition to those from the forestry and agricultural sectors, by "specialized energy crops" (Romano and Cozzi 2005; Ferreira et al. 2017) grown on marginal, unproductive lands, as well as grasses from meadows and pastures not used for livestock. Studies (Helis et al. 2021) admit that mountain areas host lands that are not suitable for food crops or other uses, classified as marginal lands. A good management of these lands is to use them to obtain biomass used for energy purposes. The Polish Sudeten mountain range becomes a study area to estimate the biomass potential of these lands. Research has shown that on these lands in the Sudeten area, production of 9.27 tons/year of dry biomass can be obtained, even after the first year (Helis et al. 2021).

We therefore observe that the biodiversity and characteristics of mountain areas provide a significant amount of biomass that could be utilized as an energy source. It is accepted that mountains, due to their natural, cultural and social riches, have been a source of testing for sustainable development solutions (Moretti et al. 2023), which can validate the potential of mountain areas to support a sustainable energy strategy.

The use of biomass as an energy source in sustainable systems could generate, at the local level, in addition to environmental benefits (Manolis et al. 2019), social benefits, such as job creation (Fernandes and Costa 2010; Ferreira et al. 2017; Manolis et al. 2019), implicitly generating additional family income and for local investors (Fernandes and Costa 2010). Another significant advantage for local communities is that related to energy security (Fernandes and Costa 2010).

The availability of energy sources represents an important pillar in the development of a country (Romano and Cozzi 2005), and this is also true at the level of a region or even area. Biomass, as an energy source, may be the best option for rural areas, which in addition to economic development offers numerous other social and environmental benefits (Saleem 2022). As a result, the availability and utilization of biomass in energy systems could lead to the sustainable development of mountain areas (Ferreira et al. 2017).

However, in order to achieve sustainability objective, the use of biomass as a renewable energy source should be consistent with the following criteria: not to compete with food and feed - in order not to undermine the main objective of agriculture, i.e. to produce food (the EU considers that the use of biomass as an energy source should be done on a small-scale (Ferreira et al. 2017)); not to lead to land degradation through overexploitation; not to trigger desertification through irrational exploitation of forest resources, and also not to be a factor in reducing biodiversity through the creation of large-scale energy monocultures.

Along with respecting the listed criteria to achieve the objectives of energy sustainability in mountain areas, a strategy should be devised as a first step to include: policies, investments, innovation and recycling.

A good energy strategy in mountain areas, based on renewable sources such as biomass, should include at least three steps: I. **Assessment** – of both the energy demand and supply of biomass in a given region. II. **Development and innovation** - to have the possibility to develop the most efficient biomass-to-energy conversion technologies, but at the same time to develop the legislative framework, to enable technical innovation and its application. III. **Identification** - to be able to find the sources of funding in order to make the technological implementation possible, "government subsidies and support" would be necessary (Saleem 2022).

c. Examples of good practice

The use of biomass as an energy source in rural areas is not new, it has been an important source of energy (especially heat energy) through its direct combustion.

Today, industrialized countries use biomass for energy at a low proportion of only 3% compared to developing countries, where rural populations (about 50% of the global population) are dependent on biomass resources for fuel (Demirbas 2004), given that more than 30% of household energy used globally comes from agricultural biomass (Saleem 2022).

Studies show that for developing countries, there would be important sources of biomass that could be used for energy purposes (Berndes et al. 2003). However, in order to be used in sustainable energy systems, biomass should come predominantly from residues, whether of a forestry nature (waste from the wood industry, residues from forest management or even wooden items from old furniture), agricultural (cereal residues, manure, food crop residues, etc.) or from land use, which are not needed for food production or other materials/materials (Berndes et al. 2003). Moreover, more efficient biomass conversion technologies are needed.

Various countries have moved to modernize technologies to convert biomass into energy more efficiently.

Thus, among the examples exposed in the specialized literature (Fernandes and Costa 2010), we can list a rural locality in Portugal (Marvão). This is characterized by villages located in valleys, among mountains, where agriculture is the main activity. A study was initiated in this region to evaluate forest and agricultural biomass residues for their use for energy purposes. The results showed that forestry residues were estimated at 2634 tons per year, while agricultural residues reached 7973 tons per year. It was concluded that, the amount of biomass available for energy purposes is significant for the study area. Furthermore, in order to illustrate the energy potential of biomass resources, a hotel in the area was taken as a case study where the heating system was modified to use biomass as a feedstock. It was concluded that the conversion of the oil-based heating system to a biomass-based system has both environmental and economic advantages for local investors.

Another study rendering biomass as a possible sustainable energy source is presented by Gurung and Oh (2013), where traditional biomass is used in modern energy systems. This study is conducted in Nepal, a low electricity country that has benefited from the "Biogas Support Program". The analysis shows that by 2010, 225350 household biogas plants had been installed in this country (the potential for household-scale biogas plants is estimated at 1.9 million due to of cattle residues). About 500,000 improved cooking stoves were also installed (with the help of foreign donors) in 48 districts of Nepal by the end of 2011. The benefits of improved cookstoves, the study's authors claim, would be to reduce harmful household gas emissions and reduce wood consumption by up to 50%, which would reduce indoor air pollution in rural households and make cooking more efficient.

The literature (Saleem 2022) also presents other examples where biomass is being used as an energy source, such as China, where over 190 million people have benefited from cooking stoves fueled by agricultural biomass; the UK, which has a 38 MW agricultural residue (straw) power plant; or Canada, which produces 5336 million liters of ethanol from agricultural biomass.

These are just a few examples of the use of biomass for energy production, which shows that sustainable solutions to fossil fuels can be found. Moreover, the use of biomass as an energy source can be a solution for energy security and sustainable development of mountain areas. However, to achieve these objectives, technological development to improve the utilization of biomass energy and additional investments are required (Nosheen and Khan 2022).

Analyzing the examples presented, we could say that there are various possibilities for using biomass in energy programs for mountain areas. Thus, taking the example of the town of Marvão in Portugal, we observe that in mountainous areas there could be an opportunity for power plants operating on conventional fuels to be transformed into biomass-based power plants. Moreover, the use of biogas in family energy systems can represent an important source of energy supply for mountainous areas.

Another possibility for using biomass as an energy source for the analyzed areas is the installation of improved stoves, which would have the advantage of reducing raw material consumption, but especially of reducing toxic gas emissions at the household level. Improved biomass stoves also have the great advantage of being able to be installed in remote and difficult-to-access areas, making it possible to meet the basic energy needs of communities in high mountain areas.

Also, the development and installation of a biomass-based power plant, serving a network of mountain communes or even a city located in mountain regions, can be another alternative for using biomass.

Therefore, it can be appreciated that both the potential and the possibilities of using biomass as an energy source for mountainous areas are considerable.

However, studies addressing the topic of mountain biomass are still few, and most often analyze a single type of biomass. Most studies related to the potential of biomass as an energy source are reported at the country level (e.g. Kaygusuz and Türker 2002, Rytter et al. 2014, Katsoulakos and Kaliampakos 2016), European level (e.g. Ericsson and Nilsson 2006, Camia et al. 2021, Janiszewska and Ossowska 2022), and even global level (e.g. Long et al. 2013, Sikkema et al. 2020), and less at the local level. It is also noted that biomass as an energy source is very rarely found in energy statistics (Kaygusuz and Türker 2002).

This fact requires the completion of studies on the topic addressed. It is necessary to conduct a detailed assessment of biomass (including all types of biomass available in a given area) at the level of mountain areas in order to make it possible to use it in local energy systems. Detailed knowledge of the quantitative and qualitative availability of biomass is the basic step in the context of planning a biomass-based energy strategy.

As a result, the purpose of this study is to participate in raising awareness of the potential and possibilities for using biomass in mountainous areas, but at the same time of the need for local and detailed research on it.

d. Future research

The theme of renewable energies together with sustainable development places biomass in the sphere of interest, due to its potential to participate, to a considerable extent, in the fulfillment of the clean energy challenge.

The theoretical work analyzing this topic aims to bring to the attention of stakeholders the importance of biomass as a renewable energy source at global as well as local level. However, it needs to be followed up with research at the level of local/mountainous regions in order to be able to develop functional and sustainable energy strategies.

For this, future research should address studies such as: identification of biomass sources in a mountain region/area; assessment of biomass supply and its availability to be used for energy purposes; respectively, analyzing of a mountain region/area in terms of energy demand and biomass supply (in the sense of how much quantity of biomass could cover the energy needs), but also analyzing the existing energy infrastructure to assess how well it can support the distribution of energy from different sources.

Such research could be a basis on which to build sustainable and efficient energy systems in mountain communities, which would ensure energy security and to contribute to the socio-economic development of the area.

CONCLUSION

Biomass is a renewable energy source with significant potential, both globally and locally. Due to its diverse character (biomass is found in different types and comes from various activities), and global distribution (it is widespread in most countries in the world), it could be among the main energy sources.

The specialized literature reveals that, in mountain areas, biomass is found in various types. Depending on the specifics of the area and its characteristics, biomass sources can be represented by residues from forestry exploitation. These can be in significant quantities due to the fairly large areas covered by forest vegetation, knowing that 23% of the forest area is hosted by mountains. Also, residues from the wood processing industry represent another source of biomass available for mountain areas. The use of unproductive marginal lands to obtain energy crops, which would generate significant quantities of biomass available to the energy sector of mountain areas, represents another source of biomass with significant potential.

Residues from agricultural crops or various plantations (for example, vineyards in countries such as Italy) are considered available biomass sources in mountain areas. Another activity, specific to mountainous areas, that generates biomass that could be used for energy purposes is animal husbandry.

Regarding the possibilities of using biomass as an energy source in mountainous areas, it can be seen that family biogas installations or improved stoves for households represent a good opportunity, especially for heavily isolated mountain communities.

Harnessing it at local level, especially in mountainous areas where it is abundant and from different sources such as agriculture and forestry, could lead to economic development and energy security. The economic benefits will also be felt by local

investors. It is also accepted that obtaining energy from renewable sources such as biomass also has numerous environmental advantages.

Moreover, a biomass-based energy system could reach remote, mostly isolated areas, where it could provide their energy needs.

However, the transition to a renewable energy system (in this case biomass) needs research as a foundation, policies and government support, but last but not least funding.

The main research directions in the future regarding the use of biomass in mountain energy systems should include the evaluation of all types of biomass existing at the local level. The existing literature on this topic most often focuses on one or two types of biomass, generally agricultural and/or forestry biomass, or the biomass potential of a region should include all types of biomass (forestry, agricultural, household waste, wood from used furniture, livestock residues, respectively the potential for biomass cultivation on unproductive marginal lands).

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